

Research article

Lexical forms and their distribution of the word for ‘yesterday’ in Yunnan Tibetan

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Abstract: This article describes the word forms for ‘yesterday’ in Kham Tibetan varieties spoken in Yunnan, China, and analyses their distribution. It confirms two types of word forms: Type A, corresponding to Literary Tibetan *kha rtsang* (A1) and its derivations (A2); and Type B, of unclear origin. Type B is isolated to the mBalhag dialect, whereas the remaining varieties belong to Type A. This discussion focuses on the sound shape of Type A owing to this situation. The Nyishe subgroup displays a distinctive feature that involves restructuring the second syllable’s *r*-preinitial into the final consonant of the first syllable. This phenomenon is specific to the subgroup, and this article interprets it as a local innovation resulting from phonological features.*

Keywords: Tibetic; Kham Tibetan; lexical distribution; expansion; syllabic restructure

1. Introduction

This article describes word forms for ‘yesterday’ in Kham Tibetan varieties in the Tibetosphere of Yunnan Province (henceforth, Yunnan Tibetan), and then examines how they are distributed from a geolinguistic viewpoint. According to Tournadre and Suzuki (2023:823), two word forms for ‘yesterday’ are mainly utilised in Tibetic languages: *kha rtsang* and *mdang* (literally meaning ‘last night’) in Literary Tibetan (LT).

In Yunnan Tibetan, *kha rtsang* is widespread with some phonetic modifications or derivational changes. However, etymological information on the form *kha rtsang* is unknown. A syllable-by-syllable analysis has not yet been performed. However, based on derivational morphology, the first syllable *kha* is also used in words, such as *khas*

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nyin ‘the day before yesterday’ and *kha nub* ‘last night’, and hence it can be considered to be a core semantic part of ‘the day before the reference point’.

In Literary Tibetan, the regular spelling is *kha rtsang*; however, *kha sang* is also accepted, reflecting the sound reality of several Tibetic languages. In addition, various pronunciations appear, such as *kha rtsa* in Dzongkha and *kha'i sa* in Lhasa. This is also the case in Yunnan Tibetan.

Fig. 1 Classification of Yunnan Tibetan.

Before a discussion of the forms of ‘yesterday’ in Yunnan Tibetan, I display Figure 1, showing the most recent dialectal classification of these varieties (Suzuki 2022b, 2023) with two key areas: A-rGyalhang Town and B-Tacheng Town. Geographical information contains rivers (sky blue) and main traffic roads (brown). This area is in

the south-eastern corner of the Tibetosphere, and other ethnic languages are spoken in contact with Tibetic (see Roche and Suzuki 2018).

2. Word forms

Two forms are distinguished for the word for ‘yesterday’ in the target varieties: Type A, *kha rtsang* and its derivational forms; and Type B, /'da l̥ʂ/, of an unclear origin. The two forms are classified as follows:

Type A

A1: a disyllabic form corresponding to the LT form (e.g., /k^ha^hts̥ʂ/ and /'k^hə- ts̥ʂ/).

A2: a trisyllabic form with the first and second syllables' initial as /k^h/ and /ts/, respectively (e.g., /'k^hɛ tsə mʌ/).

Type B

/'da l̥ʂ/ only.

The above classifications do not distinguish between detailed variations in pronunciation. Type A1 exhibits diversity; however, every sound shape corresponds to LT *kha rtsang*. Type A2 is a word consisting of LT *kha rtsang* and a suffix *ma*. However, the factors related to the addition of the last morpheme are uncertain.

Notably, Tibetic languages in Yunnan are unlikely to use a form corresponding to LT *mdang*. Although Type B contains /d/, it does not correspond to the LT *md* initial since the spelling *md* generally corresponds to a prenasalised initial /ⁿd/ or even a nasal /n/ in Yunnan Tibetan (cf. Suzuki 2016, 2018), whereas its second syllable, /l̥ʂ/, can correspond to LT *sang*. However, it is difficult to confirm whether Type B is related to LT *sang*, a variant of *rtsang* in LT *kha rtsang*. Moreover, except for Type B, word forms developed in Yunnan or its contacting regions, as well as borrowings, are not attested.

3. Geographical distribution and its analyses

Figure 2 illustrates the geographical distribution of the three types of word forms mentioned above. Type A1 is the most widespread type, whereas Types A2 and B are geographically characterised.

Type A2 is distributed in the south of the map, in Weixi County. It is employed in varieties belonging to the Melung subgroup (in a narrow sense, except for Phongpa; see Suzuki 2024a for the classification) of the Sems-kyi-nyila group. The varieties

spoken in Tacheng Town use different types of word forms for ‘yesterday’ depending on the dialectal groups (Fig. 3). The word forms do not seem to have an influence beyond the subdialectal groups. An interpretation of the case of Phongpa is concerned with the archaicity of Types A1 and A2. When A1 is older than A2, innovation occurs in the central Weixi area of the Melung subgroup. By contrast, if the ABA distribution is applied, then A2 is older than A1; hence, Phongpa’s form A1 is replaced by A2 through a borrowing process from a neighbouring variety.

Fig. 2 Word forms for ‘yesterday’.

Type B is isolate at mBalhag. It is difficult to explain its origin owing to the lack of sources of word forms and the migration history of mBalhag Tibetans (see Suzuki 2013).

Fig. 3 Word forms for ‘yesterday’. Weixi area enlarged.

Type A1 can be further analysed based on its phonological form. The first syllable’s rhyme (vowel plus final, if any) is focused on, corresponding to LT *a* in *kha rtsang*, as this part exhibits great variation among the varieties. Hypothesised factors triggering the variation are indicated as a difference in the regularity of the sound correspondence with LT *a#* and a difference in prosodic features (iambic or trochaic; see Suzuki 2022a:299-300). Figure 4 shows the phonological description of the target feature (i.e., the rhyme form of Type A1’s first syllable), which is analysed according to the vocalic types with symbols.

Fig. 4 Type A1's rhyme forms (sound correspondence of *a* in *kha*).

Fig. 5 Type A1's rhyme forms or sound correspondence of *a* in *kha*. Central area enlarged for the distribution of the forms with a final (square symbols).

The first three low-vowel types follow a general sound correspondence with LT *a#* for each variety. Particularly, the sound correspondence with the vowels /ɛ/ and /a/ belongs to the minority within the Tibetic languages (Tournadre and Suzuki 2023:252).

The square symbols represent a type with a final (/r/ and /j/) and are distributed in the central area (along the Jinshajiang River) and to the west (along the Lancangjiang River). This type is striking because a restructuring of two syllables was observed.

Meanwhile, the circle symbols front mid-vowels, in general, do not correspond to LT *a#*, even though the prosodic feature is considered. It is reasonable that rhymes /ar/ and /aj/ (square symbols) evolved into /ɛ/ or /e/ (circle symbols). This process has been observed in various Tibetic varieties of Yunnan (Suzuki 2018:47-48). Long vowels are indicative of an ongoing sound change process whereby a rhyme consisting of a vowel + a final evolves into a short vowel; however, the vowel length is influenced by various prosodic features as well as each variety's phonological system. The historical order of the vowel length cannot always be assessed. It is noteworthy that all of these features appear in the central area (Fig. 5).

Figure 6 shows the simplified types of Type A1's rhyme, reflecting the variations and archetypes shown in Figure 4. The rhyme is classified into the following three types:

- A: low vowel type, following the regular sound correspondence with LT *a#*
- B: mid-vowel type

C: final's potential existence type

Fig. 6 Simplified classification of Type A1's rhyme.

Type A is unmarked; hence, its distribution is less valuable from the perspective of locality. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that Type A appears in the northern zone, the Chaphreng group, the sPomtserag and Bodgrong subgroups, and part of the nJol subgroup of the sDerong-nJol group.

Type B has two origins. As mentioned earlier, the emergence of mid-vowels originated from a prosodic pattern (iambic) and the evolution of rhymes from Type C.

Type B appears around Type C, for which we consider an ABA-distribution; however, Type C is likely to be an older form than Type B.

Type C includes r-final and j-final. The r-final can change into j-final under certain conditions, following the general tendency of sound changes attested in various Tibetic languages (Tournadre and Suzuki 2023:254). For Type C distributed in the west part, a similar sound change process is attested in some words with a r-final, as in *dkar* ‘white’: $ar > a^y > aj > \varepsilon$ (Suzuki 2011).

After the sound change processes are considered, two hypotheses are proposed:

- (1) $A > B$; and
- (2) $A > C > B$.

The former is a change triggered by the local prosodic feature, that is, /a/ corresponding to LT *kha* (*rtsang*) changed into another mid vowel, whereas the latter is a change in which the segmental features between syllables are restructured, such as LT *kha rtsang* > **khar tsang*. Therefore, these two processes are independent.

Process (1) reflects a natural sound change process, whereas Process (2) is not analysed as a regular sound change owing to the lack of parallel examples. Presently, a similar syllable restructure happens only in the word for ‘nineteen’ corresponding to LT *bcu dgu* > **bcur gu* (Suzuki 2024b). In Yunnan Tibetan, Process (1) belongs to the minority and is found in north-western parts (Fig. 6). This type is likely to be separated from the varieties that use process (2) by Type A (slash), as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7 Simplified classification of Type A1's rhyme (enlarged).

The r-final form of Type C is characterised by varieties in the Nyishe subgroup of rGyalthangic of the Sems-kyi-nyila group (Suzuki 2019, 2024a). These varieties are spoken in the periphery of the rGyalthangic-speaking region; hence, Types B and C exhibit an ABA distribution, although distorted, because Type C is a retention of the older form and Type B, as a new form, expands from the centre (rGyalthang Town, the local economic centre) to its surrounding areas. The ABA-distribution with rGyalthang as the centre is also attested in the word form for ‘today’ (Suzuki 2023).

The archaicity of Type C maintained in Nyishe is probably owing to its geographical isolation in the steep valley. However, a principal road (National Route 214; G214 in Fig. 1) penetrates the area to connect rGyalthang with nJol. Hence, language contact has become more frequent following the augmentation of local traffic, which has brought changes to the Nyishe varieties. Indeed, the Thangstod variety of Nyishe, spoken in the easternmost area of Nyishe’s distribution region in contact with the rGyalthang varieties, exhibits a similarity in the r-final form to the rGyalthang varieties (Suzuki 2019).

4. Conclusion

This article examined the lexical forms for ‘yesterday’ in Tibetic languages in the Yunnan Tibetosphere. Except for a single variety (mBalhag) using /‘da ɬ̥/, all the varieties employ a word derived from or related to LT *kha rtsang* ‘yesterday’. The latter is further classified into two groups: disyllabic and trisyllabic. The trisyllabic form is limited to the Melung subgroup of Weixi County. The disyllabic form is distributed in the widest region and three types are found based on the first syllable’s rhyme. These types reflect the change process in which a new form expands from the local centre, rGyalthang, to its periphery, forming an ABA-distribution.

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